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Measures of Cognitive and Psycho-Physiological Response to a Virtual Driving Assistance

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Abstract:

In recent times, as driving functionalities become more automated, motorists run the most likely risk of becoming cognitively removed from the driving procedure. First-time drivers need to be more comfortable with driving skills before an attempt at real-life test procedures and psychophysiological measures provide added value that may not be captured through behavioural subject measures. This paper provides intelligent analytics for mobile test driving that registers eye movement behaviour based on mapped fixation on the x and y coordinates of the Cartesian of a virtual driving scene for users, its features integrate physiological measures such as the Pupil changes, SCR and ST. The model provides measures that can be utilised to assess the cognitive state of users in virtual driving environments. The importance of psychophysiological measures within the context of safety is discussed and the commonly used physiological metrics indices of the cognitive state are looked into as a potential metric that would be relevant for the driving research field.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Current research is focussing on constantly working on methods that improve driving performance in users by assessing cognitive states either in real-time or in a virtual environment [20, 22, 15, 5, 3]; these cognitive states could be the workload, ergonomics, inattention and probably fatigue. The major way to improve the assessment of subtle cognitive states is to adopt a multimodal approach that measures the changes in the nervous system to sense near real-life information about the cognitive states of the person [17, 8, 9, 27, 29]. Such a method of assessment can promote the development of an advanced driving assistant that can be able to predict and possibly augment a risky driving behaviour that might be encountered during a real-life scenario.

In most cases, cognitive states are assessed using subjective, behavioural and physiological measures, using subjective assessment can sometimes be limiting if it is disruptive to real-time tasks such as the primary intrusion. Users may

not always be accurate in making a subjective judgement about their emotional and cognitive states, such a case can be in their workload, visual attention and fatigue level in the case of a real-life situation [28, 14, 30, 23, 24]. Cognitive states such as mental workload are based on the multimodal and faceted concept and subject measures cannot be used alone to access it, but multiple measures such as physiological and performance metrics are warranted to improve and complement extended behavioural metrics and improve cognitive load and state changes in the cognition of a user. As the trend in automation becomes more likely to become prevalent in real-time, monitoring of users' behaviour may reduce in assessment as there are fewer analytic procedures embedded in the virtual driving model. There is a need for more analytics on user behaviour and cognition to be integrated into a virtual world of a driving scene. This will make non-behaviour metrics to be more relevant to incorporate in the understanding of users' cognitive states in virtual training tests [13, 26, 19, 21, 18].

Intelligent analytics in driving assistance systems should be capable of applying sense and assessing distraction on the cognitive level of the driver to be able to augment safe driving conditions and ergonomics of a user for a real-life training session [6, 10, 11, 1, 16]. Building a reliable system is paramount in such cases because they would be able to predict the decreased level of vigilance or risky levels in the cognitive load that would help in augmentation in a short time frame. This paper contributes to this area of research by developing multimodal intelligent analytics that registers users' or drivers' cognitive load and performance both in terms of their eye movement behaviour and correlates to multimodal physiological measuring metrics.

The psycho-physiological metrics are used to assess the degree of arousal or an active state and the use of multiple psycho-physiological constructs can also influence variations in the physiological measures [2, 7, 25, 4, 12]. Skin conductance response, Skin temperature and Pupil changes are mild but sensitive to psychological constructs such as workload and stress. These metrics can be used to augment the concept ability in the cognitive state of users in driving assistance. The proceeding sections discuss methods of experimental study and results obtained.

2 METHOD

The initial stage of the project is developing intelligent analytics, that is not only open to modifications for subsequent methods in the area of psycho-physiological but also as a means of applying multimodal measuring physiological sensors for registering users' cognitive state in real-time virtual testing driving scenarios. The application was implemented in MATLAB with an integrated JAVA library for both data generation and real-time physiological monitoring of users' cognitive states. The design modules are then tested on five participants by asking them to sit in front of the PC with the embedded virtual driving assistance (Figure 1), the tool is then used to monitor their cognitive workload and eye movement behaviour in synch with their physiological response to user task. The user behaviour is set to correlate and synchronize with physiological responses with a similar timestamp and latency level to the hand-clap signal. The generated data from the PC is sent to another system that helps to analyse and predict user response in synch to task performance and workload. All system connected in data sharing and transfer is wirelessly enabled for easy access to data and data visualisation. The tool was first designed for a mobile view version and can be assessed on a PC as a standalone. The test and performance metrics for both cognitive load in eye movement and input physiological parameters are also analysed for the system's reliability, this is discussed in the subsequent sections.

$$\begin{aligned} E_a(t) &= R_a i_a + L_a \frac{di_a(t)}{dt} + K_b \frac{d\Theta_m(t)}{dt}; \\ T_m(t) &= K_i i_a(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_m(t) &= J \frac{d^2\Theta_m(t)}{dt^2} + B \frac{d\Theta_m(t)}{dt} + K\Theta_m(t); \\ E_a(t) &= K_a e(t); E(t) = K_\delta [\Theta_r(t) - \Theta_m(t)]; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The state variables for the given system are assigned as follows: $x_1(t) = \Theta_m(t)$, $x_2(t) = \frac{d\Theta_m(t)}{dt}$ and $x_3(t) = i_a(t)$. The state-space representation of the expressions is given in the form:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = Ax(t) + B\Theta_r(t) \quad (3)$$

$\Theta_m(t) = Cx(t)$, where $\Theta_m(t)$ is the output physiological response while $\Theta(t)$ is the input matrix with physiological response variables.

$$\frac{\theta_m(s)}{\theta_r(s)} = \frac{L(\Theta_m(t))}{L(\Theta(t))} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: User sitting in front of PC with Virtual driving assistance while their physiological readings are recorded and generated.

3 RESULT

The model was tested on two different stages, the index page of the driving assistance and the middle stage for multiple motorists on the virtual highway. The procedures used in this paper are based on an innovative way of determining the driving context for a driving assistance system. In Figure 2, we invoked the use of variables that best describes the context of the environment, the index page and the eye movement behaviour and pupil changes based on dilation and constriction to the cognitive response to the virtual driving assistance used as the stimuli. A training set based on control dynamics (Equation 1) is a set that stores driving situation patterns made by eye movement behaviour and from which the system consults to determine the cognitive response of the user. The pattern is categorised into "stress" (constriction) and "relaxed" (dilation). The control moto dynamics make predictions based on this. The driving behaviour of the users is an input to the model process that yields the action that is implemented when the user needs to be informed about certain situations such as the cognitive level of the user which is reflected on the virtual screen. Figure 1 shows the cognitive response where the user's gaze points on fixation location were mostly dilated not based on drowsiness but on the situation at hand such as the reaction to an "emergency" stop to a road barricade in front of the driver. This is set to the system to recognise and send an alert on such a situation if the case arises.

Figure 2 shows the second phase of the task with multiple motorists on the scene, the driving situation is an input that yields the action that the driver must take to be informed and then be assisted in the driving situation. The action is mostly directed to the driver such as reducing cognitive workload where eye constriction is in excess and a relaxed mood is needed to override an uncontrollable situation.

Figure 4 shows the index page of the analytics tool used to synchronise the pupil changes (green line) with time continuously with the other physiological response. Phasic changes and tonic phases can be detected and set to a minimal level depending on the cognitive response that exceeds normal reaction. Each cognitive response detected is based on the response peaks (Tonic and phasic). The fingers prints are a simple read data matrix made by input images from fingers placed in the multimodal measuring sensor. The metrics used in determining the optimal response depend on the baseline (cyan color). The SCR (red) is the electrical changes of the skin as a result of moisture content coursed on the skin while the user is involved with the virtual driving assistance stimuli. The performance metric for each physiological parameter is also calculated to determine the predictive accuracy of each of the input attributes.

Figure 5 shows the performance for each response parameter for the physiological measuring sensor. The SCR and ST have a high impact on the response to virtual stimuli for the mapped fixation on the y-coordinate and x-coordinate of the Cartesian plane. Each continuous response is detected with a low rate of 0.6% and is most significant based on

Figure 2: The index page of driving assistance: the pupil measured based on constriction and dilation in the virtual interface.

Figure 3: The multiple motorists on the road page with both eye constriction and dilation response on the virtual scene indicate the cognitive response of trying to avoid a bad situation.

the third-order used in response reaction prediction. The mapped fixation on the y-coordinate of the 3D plane and pupil changes has a low impact on the response prediction to the virtual content on both mapped x and y Cartesian plane, with an error rate of 0.001%, this is also good in terms of system reliability. The rationale for embedding a system report is to enhance the content in both aspects of analysis and visualisation.

Figure 4: The index page of the Analytical tool records and visualise the physiological response of the driver and as an incision for alert control.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the possibility of developing mobile intelligent analytics on the performance of cognitive and psycho-physiological responses to driving assistance. The challenges for valid and reliable quantification and qualitative research in a driving assistance scenario are less predictable in real-life driving settings. Virtual settings for driving assistance are designed to set a framework for monitoring and predicting users' cognitive response to virtual driving assistance. This is enabled by a multimodal physiological measuring sensor that records users' eye movement behaviour in synch with their physiological response. We also discussed measures that may be better suitable in a real-life situation. Such as detecting the cognitive response of the users and being able to predict the high level of stress experienced in a given situation by minimising the level of cognitive load on the user. This paper synthesises the work in some literature on vehicle psycho-physiological measures that help to advance the development and contribution to the effective human-machine interfaces and driver support systems. The future perspective is to embed the tool in a real-life driving scene that test and monitors the driver's cognition through a first-time driving scene and be able to predict and respond to users' stress level during the risky situation in real time.

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Figure 5: Performance for each response parameter for the physiological measuring sensor.

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